

**PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROFESSIONAL
DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS****Khuda-Zade Konul***Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
Department of Pedagogical Psychology
orcid.org/0000-0002-0374-6911
Konul.xuda-zada@adpu.edu.az*

Abstract: This article describes the psychological features and aspects of the professional development of professors and teachers. The directions of professional development of professors, subjective characteristics of self-awareness, the ability to show correct directions in interpersonal relations, and indicators of meaningful life directions are revealed.

Keywords: faculty, professional development, self-concept, title, teacher strategy, personal development.

Integration of science, education and practice in modern psychology, pedagogy: problems and solutions requires an approach with special attention to raising the level of professional training of specialists. Professors and teachers of higher education have a great responsibility in front of our society.

The professor-teacher helps to determine the needs of students, their educational goals, skills and knowledge, and accordingly conducts the educational process, solves problems by organizing what interactive methods and what materials to work on, what goals to achieve clearly.[1, page. 87]

In the current conditions, the demands of the society on higher education professors are increasing day by day, and the task of correctly solving these demands in practice depends on highly qualified professors. The task of a professor-teacher is to teach students how to acquire professional knowledge, to form students' educational activities and thinking during classes. It is the teacher who trains the student in intellectual and professional activities and participates in the intellectual

and moral formation of the student's personality. The professor-teacher works as a custodian and carrier of various social benefits of the whole people, their everyday, cultural, moral, intellectual and spiritual values. Collecting and mastering these values, he conveys them to the younger generation according to his ability.

The student should be able to properly manage the interaction between young people, as a member of the pedagogical team, directly participates in the organization of the institution's life activities, works with students' parents, and gives lectures in front of the public. Conducts conversations, and is also a presenter of knowledge. Such a large number of tasks is understandable for the demands of higher education on professors and teachers. It is known that pedagogical activity is one of the most complex areas of human labor. For students, professors are the main figure in higher education.[2, page. 34]

Professors and teachers of higher education are different from teachers working in other education. The most important features of higher education are that professors and teachers increase their professional knowledge, respect their profession, show love for their profession, and feel a high level of social responsibility.

Therefore, the contribution of professors and teachers of higher education in the development of high-level personnel for our society is very large. They should be able to be an example to students and young people in every way. Studying the socio-psychological features of the professional development of professors is one of today's urgent issues. What do we mean by professional development of professors and teachers?

Professors-teachers have a higher pedagogical skill with a scientific title, have scientific achievements and are engaged in pedagogical work in higher educational institutions that have passed the state accreditation or in scientific institutions that implement the educational programs of higher educational institutions. employees are meant.

The professional development of professors-teachers means that the spiritual-religious, intellectual and physical abilities of the specialist are highly developed. The qualities of professional development of professors must be distinguished. They are professional sphere, family and human relations, interpersonal communication, education of students, increase of spiritual and educational knowledge, self-development and self-improvement.[3, page. 112]

In our experience of distinguishing the qualities of professional maturity of professors-teachers, each pedagogue paid great attention to which qualities he developed. These qualities of professional development are related to the increasing experience of the pedagogue.[7, page. 96] However, special attention is not paid to the professional qualities and knowledge of professors-teachers in their work. Unfortunately, we do not have enough psychodiagnostic work and psychocorrection services that serve the comprehensive improvement of higher education professors and teachers, or determine the professional maturity of professors and teachers.

Today, in an era of rapid development of science and technology, highly qualified professors require scientifically based evidence and scientific research with a clear dimension that serves the professional advancement.

At the time of major reforms in the educational system, highly qualified professors and teachers should not only have professional knowledge, they should develop spiritual and educational knowledge, and train pedagogues with a humanitarian character. It is necessary for professors and teachers to carry out their professional knowledge in an integrated manner.[4, page. 56]

The professional development of professors-teachers, having knowledge and good morals is extremely necessary in providing education to young people, therefore, it is necessary to be responsible for education and education. The essence, structure, problems and formation mechanisms of the professional development of the professor-teacher should be scientifically studied. The rapid flow of modern life creates new problems for a person, new problems arise that need to be solved in order to live accordingly. Today, it is necessary for the professional development of

the professor-teacher to be in the entire educational system of the society.[5, page. 90]

Professional maturity is the conformity of a person's professional development to the level usually achieved by people of his age, the main signs of professional maturity:

Therefore, it is important for a specialist to learn to solve both the traditional problems of higher education and the problems of modern life in order to prepare for the successful independent solution of the problems that will inevitably arise in the process of professional development.[6, page. 117]

It is the professional duty of every professor, regardless of his specialty. Subjective characteristics of professors are interrelated with self-awareness, ability to show correct directions in interpersonal relations, and indicators of meaningful life directions.

Their desire for self-improvement, an overly positive view of human nature can have various consequences for the formation of the maturity of a psychologist's personality, which is also related to his moral level. The purpose of our scientific research is to study the psychological characteristics of the professional development of the professor as a factor of his effective work.

REFERENCES

1. The term "professor" in different dictionaries. Date processed: October 28, 2019. Archived from the original on October 30, 2016.
2. K. Guba, T. Zimenkova, M. Safonova, S. Chuykina, M. Sokolov. Kak stanoviyatsya professorami: akademicheskie career, rynki i vlast v pyati stranax. — M.: 2022. — 832 p. — ISBN 978-5-4448-0280-9.3. Ethics professor. Opyt collective reflexii: collective monograph / pod ed. V. I. Bakshtanovsky; sost. M. V. Bogdanova. — Tyumen: TIU, 2020. — 232 p. — (Series "Biblioteka zurnala "Vedomosti prikadnoy etiki"". Vypusk 2). ISBN 978-5-9961-2380-3
4. Geoffrey J. Barton. The UK Academic System: hierarchy, students, grants, fellowships and all that [Copyright © G. J. Barton, 2014] (English). — ««...The most senior academic job title is professor. Professors are said to hold a chair in a subject or subject area. (page 6)". Data processing: October 22, 2016. Archived from the original on October 30, 2019. 592 p.5. Halpern D. Psychology critical thinking. Peter. 2021.
6. L.V. Climbery, N.V. Yadrova, R.M. Nurzhanova, Modern approaches to the formation of students' cognitive activity // Modern problems of science and education. - 2017. - No. 6;
7. G.I. Shchukin. Pedagogical problems of forming students' cognitive interests: textbook /. - M.: Pedagogy, 2020 .-- 296 p.